

01
Newsletter

July 2024

REBECCA

Reconfigurable Heterogeneous Highly Parallel
Processing Platform for safe and secure AI

Website www.rebecca-chip.eu
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Co-funded by
the European Union

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Solver Intelligent Analytics

EDDL integration into Bonseyes platform.

EXAPSYS

A functional quad-core RISC-V processor capable of booting Linux is available on the emulation platform. A custom AXI4 Network on Chip (NOC) has been developed to integrate AI and security accelerators. The system supports a shared global address space.

Technical University of Crete

TUC has developed a pattern-matching algorithm for IDS (Intrusion Detection System) and introduced it in the emulation platform.

SYSGO

Within the REBECCA ad-hoc Safety and Security working group, SYSGO has contributed to safety and security need analysis. As WP3 lead, it was a pleasure to work with FORTH (editor) and other WP3 partners to prepare D3.1 on the alpha version of the software stack.

Deliverables

16 Deliverables have already been prepared and submitted.

Imec

The IMEC neuromorphic AI accelerator has been developed, integrating several IBEX RISC-V cores.

Lund University

The on-chip memory AI processing module has been developed, and back-end implementation has started.

FORTH

Kubernetes/K3s has been successfully ported to RISC-V.

University of Athens

The University of Athens team has developed a novel safety/reliability assessment simulation-based framework for heterogeneous SoCs which employs fault-injection to quantify the vulnerability of the RISC-V CPU and the REBECCA accelerators to transient and permanent hardware faults when the platform is deployed at the edge.

Excellent performance results with a reduction in latency of 80%

Performance comparison
Klepsydra AI / TensorFlowLite (TFL)

Key Highlights:

- "PolarFire Icicle Kit": Utilises RISC-V architecture with SiFive's U54-MC cores and a PolarFire FPGA.
- "OBPMark-ML": An ESA initiative benchmarking framework for validating space-qualified onboard processors. Includes AI models for cloud detection, ship detection, CME detection, etc.

RISC-V, the open standard instruction set architecture (ISA) based on RISC principles, has revolutionised the tech landscape since its inception at the University of California, Berkeley in 2010. Free and open source, RISC-V's modular and simple design supports a wide range of applications, from embedded systems to supercomputers, making it a highly scalable and efficient solution. Managed by the RISC-V Foundation, its growing community and ecosystem provide a flexible and cost-effective alternative to proprietary ISAs like ARM and x86.

RISC-V is increasingly adopted for AI on the edge, thanks to its open and customisable nature. It is well-suited for edge AI applications where efficiency, low power consumption, and tailored hardware are crucial. Its modular architecture allows for custom extensions optimised for AI workloads, such as vector processing and machine learning accelerators. This flexibility enables the design of specialised processors that handle AI inference and processing directly on edge devices, reducing the need for constant cloud connectivity and enabling faster, more efficient AI operations in applications like IoT devices, smart cameras, and autonomous vehicles.

Klepsydra has benchmarked the execution of AI algorithms on the Microchip PolarFire ICICLE using ESA's OBPMark-ML models and TensorFlowLite as a baseline. The results were impressive, with Klepsydra AI running up to 5x faster than the baseline!

Press Release

Was successfully shared by these media:

DATA CENTER MARKET
EL NEGOCIO
TECNOBITT

DIRIGENTES DIGITAL
LA VOZ DE TOMELLOSO
NATION WORLD NEWS

LA COMARCA DE PUERTO LLANO
LANZA DIGITAL
OBJETIVO CASTILLA LA MANCHA

The EdgeAI AI Tech Conference

<https://edge-ai-tech.eu/conference-homepage/>

We are proud to announce that REBECCA KDT JU partners, including EXAPSYS Exascale Performance Systems, Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH), Boneyes Community Association (Non-Profit), and Lund University, recently showcased their groundbreaking innovations at the EdgeAI AI Tech Conference.

REBECCA KDT JU was a vital part of this remarkable event, driving innovation and progress in the field of edge AI.

REBECCA KDT JU (Reconfigurable Heterogeneous Highly Parallel Processing Platform for safe and secure AI) is on a mission to democratize the development of edge AI systems. This project is creating a comprehensive hardware and software stack built around a RISC-V CPU. The result? Unparalleled performance, energy efficiency, safety, and security in comparison to existing systems.

17-19 October, 2023

The Chips Joint Undertaking Launch event

www.smart-systems-integration.org/eventchips-ju-launch-event

Our team members are thrilled to be part of the Chips Joint Undertaking Launch event! We are grateful for the opportunity to contribute to success and be part of this milestone. The spirit of collaboration and shared enthusiasm has fueled our commitment to excellence, and we look forward to continuing this journey hand in hand with Chips Joint Undertaking.

30 November -
1 December, 2023

The 1st Review meeting

Many thanks to the project team for the constructive work during the first reporting period and for the collective efforts to demonstrate our achievements during the meeting. Thanks a lot to the Project Officer and the project Reviewers for every comment and recommendation. This will help us continue the project in a way that we can all be proud to have been a part of!

14 December, 2023

HiPEAC 2024

www.hipeac.net/2024/munich/#/

We are thrilled to announce our participation as co-organizers of the "Driving Next-Gen Edge AI Technologies" workshop at HiPEAC2024, alongside industry leaders like Chips Joint Undertaking, EdgeAI, ANDANTE-AI, CLEVER-project, and the NeuroKit2E!

Representatives from SINTEF, our esteemed partner, played a pivotal role in organizing the workshop, which featured insightful presentations and engaging panel discussions. It was truly an exhilarating experience diving into AI innovation at the edges, uncovering the synergies between artificial intelligence, edge computing, and the Internet of Things (IoT). Stay tuned for more updates on our journey towards driving the future of edge AI!

17-19 January ,2024

Underwater Robot for infrastructure inspection with edge AI REBECCA Chip

www.almende.nl
www.aquasmartxl.com

One of the use cases of the REBECCA chip is an underwater robot, developed by AquaSmart Engineering and Almende. The goal of this underwater robot is to inspect underwater infrastructures, like quay walls, sheet pile walls and pillars. There can be damage present on those objects, and to aid in the inspection an AI recognition algorithm is under development. This will run 'at the edge' on the REBECCA chip, and will help detect damages, like cracks in concrete walls.

The first iteration of this robot has been built in the previous months, and right now the second iteration of the robot is in the concept phase. The first version has been tested in simulation, on a workbench, in a controlled test environment (a test container), and in the river Schie in Rotterdam. Testing the robot was a lot of fun, and the results were very promising! Almende and AquaSmart Engineering are looking forward to developing and testing the second iteration, and testing the edge AI REBECCA Chip!

Example of inspection data captured in the controlled test environment

Underwater Robot being tested in the controlled test environment

Underwater robot being tested in the river Schie

Real-time defect detection in PV panels on unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) devices

www.intecs.it

Example of O&M Operations

The “Real-time Fault Detection in PV Panels on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs)” is one of the REBECCA project’s Use Case that is being developed by Intecs Solutions. The goal of this Use Case is to develop an automated Deep Learning-based model for defect detection in PV panels based on aerial images captured by IR camera mounted on board of an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) and with the processing executed directly on-board. The results of this processing will be displayed as a predicted on-ground defect positions in a 2D map of a PV plants directly visible on the remote controller of the UAV pilot.

The current state of the art for AI-based solutions in this area typically involves initial data collection by O&M operators in the field, followed by offline processing in the O&M control room via a workstation. This results in a delayed intervention by the O&M operators, which leads to higher maintenance costs.

Example of O&M Operations Introducing on-board processing bypasses the need for data transfer and enables instant analysis, reducing O&M costs while increasing maintenance effectiveness.

Our goal in this case study is to streamline the model pipeline to reduce inference time, develop leaner CNNs, and employ structured/unstructured pruning techniques to reduce the required volume and floating-point operations (FLOPs) while ensuring a good trade-off with accuracy metrics. We're also exploring the integration of GNSS receivers to increase the resolution of defect localization to single cell granularity.

In this phase we are currently working on our algorithm and in defining collaboration with the REBECCA’s subcomponents providers.

UC's Work Pipeline

AI-powered fridges that recognize food with image recognition

www.arcelik.com.tr

User interface of the HomeWhiz™ mobile application

Another use case of REBECCA involves an AI-powered fridge developed by Arcelik. In this scenario, the fridge is equipped with two cameras: one mounted on the door, capturing the interior, and the other inside the body, capturing the door. When the door is opened, these cameras are triggered to capture multiple image frames until the door is closed again. Among these frames, the best ones, which provide optimal visibility of the fridge interior, are selected using a TOF sensor that measures the distance between the door and the body. The selected pairs of images are then transferred to the cloud for image processing and analysis, after which they are sent to the related users' Arcelik-specific mobile application (HomeWhiz™) for remote monitoring of the fridge interior.

In the current cloud-based architecture of this use case, all image processing algorithms and AI-based computer vision models, including object recognition, human detection, distortion removal, and cropping algorithms, run on the cloud platform. The object recognition model identifies and localizes 33 different objects, such as eggs, milk, water, apples, and more, creating an inventory list. The human detection model checks if there is a human in an image, which may occur unintentionally, and deletes such images if any are found due to privacy reasons.

As part of the REBECCA project, edge versions of these AI models are being developed. These edge versions will initially be deployed, executed and evaluated on REBECCA emulators and eventually integrated into REBECCA chips.

High-speed damage inspection and vision in the loop on semiconductor equipment

<https://www.imec-int.com>
www.itecequipment.com

ITEC pick-and-place equipment (ADAT 3 XF)

ITEC produces pick-and-place machines used in semiconductor manufacturing. It specializes in high volume and high speed solutions that can handle extremely small dies of tens of micrometers up to medium sized dies of several millimeters.

1. glue dispense

2. die pickup

3. vision inspection

4. die place

All machines pick dies from a wafer, and transfer them onto a substrate with electrical leads. During transfer several inspections are done for quality (scratches, chipping, contamination of the die) as well as process control (alignment, rotation, missing die).

Currently, a frame-based camera is used to determine the die size and position (quality inspection is also optional). This requires a motion stop to avoid blurry pictures, which limits the machine speed to ~10 dies/second.

Event-frame and normal frame

The next generation pick-and-place machines will be designed at much higher speeds (>100 dies/second). This requires vision inspections without a motion stop. This is being tested at ITEC using an event-based camera.

Together with IMEC we are defining and testing the envisioned analysis strategy, which looks quite promising. Next step will be to implement this low-latency edge computing on the Rebecca chip using neuromorphic AI accelerators.